

A Control Model of Consumption and Distribution of Rolled Tobacco Through Participatory Action Research

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Abstract

The objective was to create a community development model to construct social measures for controlled the consumption and distribution of rolled tobacco and enforce social measures in the target community. The participants comprised 15 villages from Nong Wang Sub-district, 15 villages from Lao Luang Sub-district, and 9 villages from Nam-om Sub-district. Participatory Action Research (PAR) and action learning constituted processes and activities of the model. The created social measures are successful and mainly because of the inclusion of creating awareness to the dangers and risk from smoking tobacco, promoting well-being programs and consultation services, encouraging individuals to quit their smoking habit by using case studies and role models, limiting smoking areas, regulating village shops and resellers to strictly abide by the social measures, and to work with the research team, community leaders, and the sub-district administrative organizations in creating a healthy community.

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Introduction

Searching for a body of knowledge through Research and Development (R&D) can lead society and individuals to know oneself and the availability of their resources. R&D can add to intellectual property and empower individuals to be self-reliant and live happily. The research project, "Population's wellbeing in developing countries, Northeastern Region, Faculty of Humanities and Social Science, KhonKaen University," by the Wed Research Group and the Bath University foundation, United Kingdom, conducted fieldwork in 4 countries: Peru, Ethiopia, Bangladesh, and Thailand from 2002-2006. For Thailand, the research project was implemented in 2 areas: Northeastern Region and Southern Region. In Northeastern Region, Associate Professor Buapan Prompakping was the lead researcher. The extended research and additional work which occurred from 2010-2012 were supervised and conducted by Chalard Chantarasombat and co-researchers who were responsible for the fieldwork in Roi Et province and Kaset Wisai district (Krobbuaban & Prompakping, 2011).

During the fieldwork in 2011-2012, it was found that there were many people who were addicted to smoking rolled tobacco and cigarettes. The number of tobacco addicts was also increasing. The authors understood that through teamwork with the community, a solution could be developed to address the issue. The authors applied PAR, teambuilding techniques, and action learning activities in the construction and development of social measures to control tobacco addiction. Kaset Wisai district in Roi Et province was selected as the target area because it is a large center for growing and producing tobacco and manufacturing of rolled tobacco. A research team was formed which included 70 people (including the authors) and PAR was applied with action learning to gather input and create a model, guidelines and eventually constructed and implemented the social measures for controlling the consumption and distribution of rolled tobacco.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What are the appropriate social measures for controlled the consumption and distribution of rolled tobacco for people in the target area?
2. Do those social measures comprise "Propriety, Congruency, and Utility? And how could they include those properties?"
3. Could the constructed social measures be implemented in the target area and how?

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

1. To create a community development model for constructing social measures for the control of the consumption and distribution of rolled tobacco.
2. To apply and enforce the social measures in Kaset Wisai district.

RESEARCH FRAMEWORK

The aim of the project was to stimulate the community's administrative sector in management development. The project would also empower administrators and community leaders to be more efficient and confidently tackle the issues of supply and demand, and to implement effective solutions to social problems in a practical and systematic process through Participatory Action Research (PAR) and action learning as defined by Chantarasombat (2008) and Chantarasombat, Srisa-ard, Kuofie & Jennex (2010). The project comprises: 1) Research team preparation 2) Analysis of problem and need 3) Participatory planning 4) Implementation based on plan and development 5) Conclusions on implementation and 6) Sharing the gained knowledge. (Figure 1)

Figure 1 Action Learning Model (Chantarasombat, 2011: 635- 642)

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The context and basic information of the targeted sub-district were studied by analyzing the research data from informal, formal interviews, observations, focus group discussions, and meetings conducted at 15 villages in Nong Wang sub-district, 15 villages in Lao Luang sub-district and 9 villages in Nam-om sub-district. The 317 research forms were gathered by 6 volunteers (2 volunteers per village) who interviewed 317 households in the 39 villages. 80 individual participants, including the authors, directly participated in the project. It was a joint collaboration between the authors and the participants in creating the design, planning, and implementation of the social measures through Participatory Action Research (PAR) and action learning. Five experts provided feedback and review of the propriety, feasibility, and utility of the development and implementation of the social measures. They also suggested a handbook for the project be created for all participants.

The research project was conducted during 2011-2012. The research instruments comprise 1) the project handbook for developing the social measure for the control of the consumption and distribution of rolled, tobacco, operational planning guidelines for sub-district level, and 2) data collection instruments which include an interview form, questionnaire, and observation forms. The statistics used for data analysis included Percentage, Mean, and Standard Deviation.

RESEARCH FINDINGS

Community Development Model

The authors and participants collaborated through PAR and action learning to identify the issues and requirements for a community model to create social measures to control rolled tobacco consumption and distribution in KasetWisai district. (Figure 2)

Figure 2. Community development model for construction of social measures for controlled the consumption and distribution of rolled tobacco

The model of construction and development social measures for controlling the consumption and distribution of rolled tobacco comprised 9 steps of participatory working techniques: 1) team-work building in the area, 2) organizing conference to promote a better understanding of the people concerned, 3) surveying data concerning the condition of rolled tobacco, 4) data analysis and sending the results as feedback to the community, 5) promoting of media for publication of the situation, 6) constructing and developing of a social measures for the control of the consumption and distribution of rolled tobacco, 7) conclusion of lessons learned from putting the social measures into practice at the provincial level, 8) promoting of media creation for the enforcing of the social measures and 9) summation of the lessons learned from putting the social measures into practice at Regional Level. There were 4 levels of social measures for controlling the consumption and distribution of rolled tobacco; comprising 1) smokers in community, 2) community leaders, 3) distribution shops, and 4) the sub-district administration office of the target communities.

Consumption and Distribution of Rolled Tobacco in KasetWisai District

The problems and the current social conditions in KasetWisai district were analyzed by using problem trees diagram of the social measures at the sub-district and district level. The selected measures were those suitable for the duration of the project, budget constraints, and could be measured with indicators. The authors and the 68 co-researchers considered measures and practices that would not cause disunity and resentment in the community. Chantarasombat (2018) mentioned that the Office of Agricultural Health in KasetWisai district conducted a survey from September 21st 2017-September 25th, and found that the general public lacked the awareness to the dangers of smoking rolled tobacco. There was no measure for control, prevention, or restrictions to counter the increased numbers of tobacco addicts in the area. Verbal injunctions were often used with little or no effect. Also, there were no precise social measures for prevention and care. Statistics shored 100,000 patients from the Public Health authorities in Roi Et province and at KasetWisai hospital that the rate of sickness caused by directly smoking tobacco products included: 1) 21.60% had low or poor immunity system resulting in diabetes, 2) 5.20% had respiratory illnesses, and 4.75% has asthma. Patients who did not smoke but came into contact with tobacco by-products, such as inhaling tobacco smoke include: 1) 7.42% had low or poor immunity system leading to diabetes, 2) 7.91 had respiratory illnesses, and 3) 5.95% had asthma.

The household income and expenditures in the 3 Sub-districts comprised 128 households from Nong Wang Sub-district, 108 households from Lao Luang Sub-district, and 81 households from Nam-om Sub-district. In the Nong Wang sub-district, the highest level of income of agriculture households was 55,207 baths/year. The highest income from commercial households was 240,000 baths/year. The lowest incomes were from households engaged in labor and employed in the service sector at 6,618 baths/year. In Lao Luang sub-district, the highest income was from a commercial household at 1,500,000 baths/year. The lowest income was 2,796 baths/year. In the Nam-om sub-district, the highest income was from agriculture households which averaged 360,000 baths/year. The lowest income was in labor at 4,631 baths/year. Nong Wang sub-district had the highest level of debt with a household debt average of 34,000 Baht per year. The highest amount of money spent on buying rolled tobacco was at 5,000 Baht per year with the lowest at 848 baths/year. In the Lao Luang sub-district, the highest average debt per household was 34,000 baths per year. The highest amount of money spent on buying rolled tobacco was at 4,300 Baht with the lowest at 855 baths/year. In the Nam-om sub-district, the highest average debt per household was at 25,345 baths per year. The highest amount of money spent on buying rolled tobacco was 4,000 Baht with the lowest at 817 Baht per year.

Plan Implementation

1. Establish learning mechanisms for participants and the research team in KasetWisai district by using Participatory Action Research (PAR) and action learning.
2. Organize meetings to create knowledge, understanding, and collaboration with the participants and the community.
3. Survey the economic, social, and tobacco consumption conditions in all 3 sub-districts and 317 households.
4. Analyze the data and present the findings to the target community and participants.
5. Create promotional media, information pamphlets, and brochures to support the implementation plan.
6. Create social measures for controlled the consumption and distribution of rolled tobacco.
7. Apply and enforce the social measures into local level trials and at the sub-district administration organization.
8. Promote and create publications to support the social measures for the control of the consumption and distribution of tobacco, brochures to promote well-being, pamphlets on the health benefits of quitting tobacco, and to support the community network.
9. Summarize the lessons, knowledge, and experience learned from the development of social measures for controlling the consumption and distribution of rolled tobacco with participants and the community. Publish academic project in local and international journals.

Model Outcomes

1. Community learning mechanisms creating social measures for the control of the consumption and distribution of rolled tobacco at the sub-district level.
2. Applying and enforcing the social measures to control the consumption and distribution of rolled tobacco at sub-district and district levels.
3. The roles of community leaders and the research group in enforcing social measures.
 - General project coordinators
 - Public Relations department
 - Media Department and Communications
 - Academics
 - Monitoring and evaluations
 - Financial Secretary to coordinate implementation processes and activities with the sub-district, and district administrative offices, and coordinate with the community network.
4. Learning Process and Knowledge Management before, during, and after the application of social measures.
5. Transformation of the Community Leaders after application of Social Measures
 - 100% of Buddhist monks refrain from smoking inside the temple area.
 - The general public has a better understanding of the social measures to control the consumption and distribution of rolled tobacco.
 - Heightened campaign to stop smoking in the community and greater awareness of health hazards from smoking tobacco.
 - At least 12 community leaders quit smoking as an example for their community.
 - Limiting smoking areas
 - Strict regulations of local tobacco retailers
 - Encouragement of tobacco producers to work with the research team and contribute to a healthy community.
6. Training Report
7. Conclusion of Success Indicators
8. Research Report and submission of 20 copies to The Wellbeing and Sustainable Development Research Group (WeSD) and the Knowledge Management and Research Center for Tobacco Control (CRC). Project report and conclusion uploaded to www.health.drchalard.com.

DISCUSSION

Improvements were made through the participatory activities with the inclusion of the publication of a handbook so that the co-researchers would have a common understanding of the activities through action learning. The evaluation of the experts found that the average value of overall efficiency, the Propriety was at “The Highest” level. The Feasibility was at “The Highest” level. The Utility aspect was at “The Highest” level because the researchers designed the conceptual framework with the emphasis on action learning. The authors believe that the success of the project was due to the authors’ familiarity and experience in PAR in the 3 sub-districts while working under “The Development of Community Health for Wellbeing of Research and Development Unit for Community Strength and Knowledge Management” at Mahasarakham University from 2008-2009. Another factor in the high efficiency of the project was due to the support and research grant from the Faculty of Humanities and Social Science, KhonKaen University. The authors utilized the funds to develop a research network group that facilitated the design and construction of the research. The PAR process helped creating proper social measures for controlling the consumption and distribution of rolled tobacco. The fundamental process involves Participatory Action Research (PAR) and was created through knowledge obtained by learning by practicing. Learning by practicing or learning by doing is supported by Wasi (2019) who emphasized that the most effective community learning system has to be organized by practicing in real situations and be executed through an integrated development which will contribute to the national well-being of the nation and recommends that higher education and universities should embrace PAR. PAR is the new paradigm in education through learning by practicing and is supported by the Well-being and Sustainable Development Foundation (WeSD), KhonKaen University. The constructed social measures in this project were based on the interest and issues that were in congruence with the members of the community that were the subjects of the research. The authors and researchers also adhered to the educational administration and management of Chantarasombat, Udomboonyanupap, & Kenchaiwong (2018) which recommends that active construction of PAR, action learning and learning by practice is essential to the success of community education and learning that identify at the factors and indicators of instructional management in the Thai language for enhancing secondary school students in Nakhon Ratchasima, resulted in 6 factors and 23 indicators of work implementation and was eventually developed as a 6 module learning program for community PAR.

The development model, through PAR processes, action learning, and construction was based on Ramsot's (2007) conceptual framework which included 9 steps of PAR: 1) to prepare the community, 2) to provide training for co-researcher from the community, 3) to determine the research design, 4) to collect data, 5) to analyze the data, 6) to consult the findings with the community, 7) to create community plan, 8) to put the plan into practice, and 9) to follow up and evaluate. Fundamental PAR processes in community development and learning by doing comprise 5 steps: 1) identifying challenging problems, issues and learning opportunities, 2) building teamwork and participatory planning, 3) learning by doing, making improvements, and appropriate adjustments, 4) concluding and reflecting on the work performance, and 5) sharing the knowledge within the team and to the public.

The social measures were implemented and put into practice at the 3 sub-districts and enforced for 4-6 months. At each sub-district, the authors started the implementation by informing the community leaders and members about the project and plan implementation. Six social measures were implemented and put into actual practice at the sub-district and village levels. The research results concluded that there were 9 PAR processes required to create and implement the social measures. The activities in the research are consistent with Chantarasombat, Bubphawan & Songsri (2018) in the development of the Innovative Community for self-reliance through sufficiency economy. Learning by doing through 6 steps of knowledge management through activity management and participatory actions created 22 learning activities for the village and were finalized into a model that included 8 development working steps.

CONCLUSION

The social measures for the control of the consumption and distribution of rolled tobacco by Participatory Action Research (PAR), was established by studying related research literature and knowledge by the 68 co-researchers. The participants discussed and were interviewed in a focus group discussion. This led to the identification and construction of issues and activities that would later be used to develop effective social measures. Improvements were made to the participatory activities to include the publication of a handbook so that the co-researchers would have a common understanding of the activities through action learning. The evaluation of the experts found that the average value of overall efficiency, the Propriety was at "The Highest" level. The Feasibility was at "The Highest" level. The Utility aspect was at "The Highest" level because the researchers designed the conceptual framework with the emphasis on action learning. The propriety of the factors and indicators reviewed by academic experts was at "The Highest" level.

The results observed were used in the planning and constructing of the necessary drive mechanism in order to implement effective social measures, the development of public awareness to the dangers and risk from smoking tobacco and the manufacturing of rolled tobacco, promote well-being programs and consultation services to the public to encourage individuals to quit their smoking habit by using case studies and role models, and enforcement of social measures. These measures include limiting smoking areas and regulating village shops and resellers to strictly abide by the decisions of the community, encourage rolled tobacco producers to work with the research team, and monitor and supervision by the sub-district administrative organizations in creating a healthy community.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Recommendations for Application

Local researchers at the village, sub-district, district, or provincial levels should be individuals who can lead, organize, take responsibilities, and understand the need for regulating the consumption and sale of tobacco products. The research team should seek out cooperation and communicate with local administrative agents to build a network system for the development of their community. Community leaders should not be restricted to those who are the village's headman or chieftain but should include individuals in the community that want to better society. The addiction to smoking rolled tobacco should be brought into the village's master development plan. The village as a whole, should work together, collaborate, and enforce the agreed measures.

Recommendations for Future Research

Participatory Action Research (PAR) at the village level will benefit youths and the forthcoming generations to become leaders and resist the consumption of rolled tobacco and addictive substances. PAR can assist communities in changing bad habits, help individuals to be productive, and strive for excellence in their careers. PAR can also be implemented to improve the local and national incomes of households. Higher education institutions should promote and support research and development in relation to developing congruent social measures and a learning network system for self-reliance, prosperity, and sustainability through the sufficiency economy philosophy and development. Research and development through a mix-methods approach to creating social measures and leadership transformation project to assist in the regulation, rehabilitation from tobacco addiction should be highly recommended.

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